

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

REVIEW - ON DO CHRONIC USE OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS EFFECT YOUR BONE HEALTH?

Neelofar Shaik^{*}, Manisha S¹, Nagaraja.J², Dr. M. Prasada Rao³

M.A.M College of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Andhra Pradesh, India (Affiliated to AcharyaNagarjuna University).

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 27/02/2019

Available online

05/04/2019

Keywords

Proton Pump Inhibitor,
Acid Supression,
Bone Metabolism.

ABSTRACT

proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), obtainable with or while not a prescription, are commonly used for the treatment of acid-related disorders. Despite their easy accessibility and customary use, PPIs can have severe side effects. However, some recent epidemiologic studies have prompt a positive association between PPI therapy and also the risk of osteoporotic fractures. The potential mechanisms underlying this association could also be associated with the physiological effects of chronic acid suppression on Ca metabolism. This area has received magnified attention as a result of the reported potential adverse effect of chronic PPI treatment leading to an increased prevalence of bone fractures. This has led to an hyperbolic examination of the effects of PPIs on Ca absorption/metabolism additionally as varied cohort, case control and prospective studies of their ability to affect bone density and cause bone fractures. long-term consequence of chronic PPI use is malabsorption of key minerals within the body, namely calcium and magnesium. The loss of those minerals may lead to bone fractures or cardiac abnormalities. I will review the revealed evidence relating to these potential links and discuss their clinical implications.

Corresponding author

Neelofar Shaik

M.A.M College of Pharmacy,
Narasaraopet,
Andhra Pradesh, India.
shaikneelofar739@gmail.com ,
7396639545

Please cite this article in press as **Neelofar Shaik** et al. Review - on Do Chronic Use of Proton Pump Inhibitors Effect Your Bone Health?. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2019;9(03).

Copy right © 2019 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Proton pump inhibitor (PPIs) are on the market since the late Nineteen Eighties and have replaced the histamine₂ receptor-antagonists (H₂RAs) because the most potent category of drugs for the treatment of acid-related diseases [1]. a number of animal and human studies support the conclusion that gastric acid secretion will have an effect on the absorption of variety of nutrients, vitamins and drugs[2–5]. These medication generate over \$13.5 billion in sales (3rd largest marketing drug class) and in 2009 over 119 million PPI prescriptions were written within the US, thus they're terribly wide used, and plenty of patients still take them for extended periods of time[7,8,9]. this can be significantly true in patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) that occurs monthly in up to 400th of yankee adults, and within the proportion with moderate to severe GERD, long run maintenance treatment with PPIs is required to regulate symptoms[2,7,8,9]. Osteoporotic fractures represent a huge public health issue worldwide. within the united states alone, an calculable ten million Americans aged over 50 years have osteoporosis, whereas another thirty four million have low bone mass. Each year, an calculable 1.5 million individuals within the united states suffer an osteoporosis-related fracture, an event which will result in minimized quality of life and augmented risk of death [10,11]. Medications within the PPI category are widely offered with or while not a prescription. Currently, the U.S. market contains six PPIs, 2 of that are offered as over-the-counter product. [Table 1]

Table.1-Commercially available Proton pump inhibitors.

Drug	Dosages, mg	IV	Liquid or suspension	Generic	Over-the-counter
Omeprazole	10, 20, 40	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Esomeprazole	20, 40	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Lansoprazole	15, 30	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Dexlansoprazole	30, 60	No	No	No	No
Pantoprazole	20, 40	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Rabeprazole	20	No	No	Yes	No

Table.2- Pharmacokinetic Properties of Commercially available Proton pump inhibitors.

	Omeprazole	Esomeprazole	Lansoprazole	Dexlansoprazole	Pantoprazole	Rabeprazole
Bioavailability, %	30–40	64–90	80–85	-	77	52
Time to peak plasma level (t _{max} , hr)	0.5–3.5	1.5	1.7	1–2, 4–5	2–3	2–5
Protein binding, %	95	97	97	96	98	96.3
Half-life, hr	0.5–1	1–1.5	1.6	1–2	1–1.9	1–2
Primary excretion	Hepatic	Hepatic	Hepatic	Hepatic	Hepatic	Hepatic
Liver metabolism	CYP2C19	CYP2C19	CYP2C19	CYP2C19	CYP2C19	CYP2C19

PPIs are used for the treatment of the many gastric conditions as well as peptic ulcer disease, demolition of *Helicobacter pylori* infections, treatment and prevention of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) gastro duodenal ulcer, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome, and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD).[27] usually, these medications are prescribed because of the low incidence of side effects and superior efficaciousness compared to alternative medicine accustomed treat the same conditions.

Long-term use of PPIs and effects on calcium absorption/metabolism and bone fractures:

Limited animal and human studies show that gastric acid secretion will facilitate calcium absorption and that acid suppressants like PPIs can decrease calcium absorption and reduce bone density [13,14,15, 16-20]. An acidic environment within the stomach facilitates the discharge of ionized calcium from insoluble calcium salts, and therefore the calcium solubilisation is thought to be vital for calcium absorption [12,13,14,15, 16-20]. variety of conditions that cause hypo/achlorhydria in humans including gastrectomy, pernicious anaemia and atrophic inflammation are related to and enhanced incidence of osteoporosis and bone fracture, and it's assumed that this can be secondary to the effect of low gastric acid levels on calcium absorption .

Long-term PPI use has been related to an augmented risk of osteoporosis and reduced bone mineral density (BMD), with a 35th increased risk of fractures. the most physiological modification induced by PPI medical care is profound suppression of gastric acid secretion. gastric acid suppression results in hypergastrinemia, and may cause malabsorption of metal. both hypergastrinemia and metal malabsorption could negatively influence bone and mineral metabolism, at least in part through induction of hyperparathyroidism. calcium serves a vital role in bone health and formation, because it is a key component of hydroxyapatite (the main structural element of bone). Bone material is a major reservoir for calcium and should contain greater than ninety nine of a body's calcium [27]. The hypothesis for the mechanism of PPI-induced bone fractures is that dietary calcium absorption relies upon an acidic surroundings within the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. due to the decrease in acidity from the pharmacological impact of PPIs, a potential loss of calcium absorption happens. This reduction in metal absorption results in shrunken osteoclastic activity and thus decreases in BMD, thereby increasing fracture risk.

In March 2011, the FDA changed its osteoporosis and fracture warning. it had been concluded that OTC products don't warrant label changes to include warnings of fracture risk. Common risk factors for fractures such as a sedentary lifestyle and concomitant use of certain medications (e.g., thiazide diuretics, hormone replacement therapy, corticosteroids) are usually discovered in patients who habitually take PPIs.[27] in addition, patients who take high doses of PPIs are at higher fracture risk versus patients who take lower otc doses. [29] Finally, patients Who take PPIs for extended periods of your time (>1 year) are additional possible to experience a fracture.[28]

Data remain relatively inconclusive and conflicting regarding the magnitude of the PPI and fracture association within the absence of extra risk factors. according to the 2013 ACG guidelines, there is insufficient proof to warrant routine BMD tests, calcium supplementation, or alternative routine precautions because of PPI use.[30] In contrast, Health Canada issued an alert in April 2013 stating that patients with existing risk factors for osteoporosis should be monitored closely and may additionally receive short PPI therapy at the lowest effective dose.[31] this is often parallel to current recommendations from the FDA despite the shortage of recommendations from the ACG.[32]If calcium supplementation is indicated, use of calcium citrate is that the most popular calcium supplement in patients taking PPIs, as it will be absorbed within the absence of an acidic surroundings.

Figure.1- Calcium absorption process [33].

CONCLUSION

PPIs are an efficacious and safe drug category. they provide relief to patients in a patient-centered health care system. sadly, these agents do probably have some long-term consequences from continued use, as well as malabsorption problems and enhanced risk of infections. Clearly, PPIs should only be prescribed when there's an acceptable clinical indication. Since clinical circumstances may change over time, it is additionally necessary to periodically review the clinical want for PPI therapy. solubility, when calcium intake is adequate, variations in solubility only play a minor role within the quantity of metal that's absorbed. Therefore, patients WHO need chronic PPI therapy should be schooled to make sure adequate daily calcium intake in line with the daily suggested allowance corresponding to their age. Also, soluble calcium salts like calcium citrate and calcium contained in milk and cheese have high bioavailability for absorption in spite of gastric pH. Therefore, if financially feasible, these will be the well-liked sources of calcium for patient receiving chronic PPI therapy. If calcium carbonate should be used, the patient should be educated to take it with a meal. . The health professional can be an advocate for the patient within the hospital system or in the community by understanding these risks and fostering patient-centered care by empowering a well-informed patient in health care decisions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The review was partially supported by M.A.M College of Pharmacy, Narasaraopeta. Greatly thankful to Dr.Prasada Rao sir and Nagaraja mam for the informative guidance on this topic and also to my colleagues. I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my review helpers for giving me the opportunity to do so. More Recommend future Research on this process has to be done.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

AIM & OBJECTIVE OF WORK

To evaluate the effect of long-term use of PPIs on bone.

JUSTIFICATION

Various studies stated that there is a link between bone health and long term usage of proton pump inhibitors but there is no perspicuity.

So the study was done to review the revealed evidence relating to these potential links and discuss their clinical implications.

REFERENCES

1. Wolfe M. Overview and comparison of proton pump inhibitors for the treatment of acid-related disorders. In: Basow DW, ed. *UpToDate*. Waltham, MA: UpToDate; 2013.
2. Lahner E, Annibale B, Delle Fave G. Systematic review: impaired drug absorption related to the co-administration of antisecretory therapy. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 2009;29:1219–1229. [PubMed]
3. Jensen RT. Consequences of long-term proton pump blockade: Highlighting insights from studies of patients with gastrinomas. *Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol*. 2006;98:4–19. [PubMed]
4. Annibale B, Capurso G, Delle Fave G. The stomach and iron deficiency anaemia: a forgotten link. *Dig Liver Dis*. 2003;35:288–295. [PubMed]
5. McColl KE. Effect of proton pump inhibitors on vitamins and iron. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009;104 (Suppl 2):S5–S9. [PubMed]
6. Jensen RT. Consequences of long-term proton pump blockade: Highlighting insights from studies of patients with gastrinomas. *Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol*. 2006;98:4–19.
7. DeVault KR, Talley NJ. Insights into the future of gastric acid suppression. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2009;6:524–532.
8. Heidelbaugh JJ, Goldberg KL, Inadomi JM. Overutilization of proton pump inhibitors: a review of cost-effectiveness and risk[corrected] *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009;104 (Suppl 2):S27–S32. [PubMed].
9. Raghunath AS, O'Morain C, McLoughlin RC. Review article: the long-term use of proton-pump inhibitors. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 2005;22 (Suppl 1):55–63. [PubMed]
10. Leibson CL, Tosteson AN, Gabriel SE, et al. Mortality, disability, and nursing home use for persons with and without hip fracture: a population-based study. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*. 2002;50:1644–50. [PubMed]
11. Chrischilles EA, Butler CD, Davis CS, et al. A model of lifetime osteoporosis impact [erratum appears in *Arch Intern Med* 1922 Mar;152(3):655] *Archives of Internal Medicine*. 1991;151:2026–32. [PubMed]
12. Lodato F, Azzaroli F, Turco L, et al. Adverse effects of proton pump inhibitors. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol*. 2010;24:193–201. A recent general review of all adverse effects of PPIs including the absorption of vitamins and nutrients and possible effects on bone fractures. [PubMed]
13. Yang YX, Lewis JD, Epstein S, Metz DC. Long-term proton pump inhibitor therapy and risk of hip fracture. *JAMA*. 2006;296:2947–2953. One of the two large case control studies that first raised the possible important association of long-term PPI use with bone fractures. [PubMed]
14. Insogna KL. The effect of proton pump-inhibiting drugs on mineral metabolism. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2009;104 (Suppl 2):S2–S4.
15. Fournier MR, Targownik LE, Leslie WD. Proton pump inhibitors, osteoporosis, and osteoporosis-related fractures. *Maturitas*. 2009;64:9–13.

16. Chonan O, Takahashi R, Yasui H, Watanuki M. Effect of L-lactic acid on calcium absorption in rats fed omeprazole. *J Nutr Sci Vitaminol (Tokyo)* 1998;44:473–481. [PubMed]
17. O’Connell MB, Madden DM, Murray AM, et al. Effects of proton pump inhibitors on calcium carbonate absorption in women: a randomized crossover trial. *Am J Med.* 2005;118:778–781. [PubMed]
18. Sipponen P, Harkonen M. Hypochlorhydric stomach: a risk condition for calcium malabsorption and osteoporosis? *Scand J Gastroenterol.* 2010;45:133–138. [PubMed]
19. Yu EW, Blackwell T, Ensrud KE, et al. Acid-suppressive medications and risk of bone loss and fracture in older adults. *Calcif Tissue Int.* 2008;83:251–259. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
20. Wright MJ, Sullivan RR, Gaffney-Stomberg E, et al. Inhibiting gastric acid production does not affect intestinal calcium absorption in young healthy individuals: a randomized, crossover controlled clinical trial. *J Bone Miner Res.*

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

- Convenient online manuscript submission
- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- International recognition
- No space constraints or color figure charges
- Immediate publication on acceptance
- Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories
- Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

